

Synthesis of Some N-(5-aryl-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl)aceta/benzamidines as Potential Fungicides

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Several N-(5-aryl-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl)aceta/benzamidines(II) have been prepared by condensing methyl/phenyl cyanides with 2-amino-5-aryl-1,3,4-thiadiazoles(I). The amidines(II) have been screened for their fungicidal activities against *Aspergillus niger* and *Aspergillus flavus*, and the results have been discussed.

BY virtue of incorporating $\text{>N}-\text{C}-\text{S}-$ moiety, the toxophoric importance of which has been well-stressed in many fungicides¹⁻⁴, a thiadiazole ring may be expected to display fungicidal activity. Various amidines are also known to exhibit useful fungicidal, bactericidal and trypanocidal properties^{5,6}. It was, therefore, speculated that N-thiadiazolylamidines(II) might be potential fungicides.

In view of above, we considered it of interest to synthesise the title amidines and to evaluate their antifungal activities. These amidines were prepared according to the Scheme 1, and were characterised by elemental analysis and i.r. spectra.

Scheme 1

The i.r. spectra of the amidines(II) revealed characteristic absorption bands in the region 1650-1680 cm^{-1} due to the exocyclic $\text{C}=\text{N}$ group, and in the range 1620-1635 cm^{-1} due to $\nu\text{C}=\text{N}$ of the thiadiazole nucleus. A medium band, attributable to $\nu\text{N}-\text{H}$, appeared around 3400 cm^{-1} . Moreover, all the amidines exhibited the i.r. bands in the regions which were clearly attributable to the substituted benzene nuclei.

All the title compounds (II) have been screened for their antifungal activities against *A. niger* and *A. flavus*. Although all the amidines were fungitoxic, the degree of their fungicidal action was not so encouraging as might be expected from the combined performance of the two moieties (the thiadiazole and the amidine).

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Experimental

The i.r. spectra were taken in nujol on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer (model 257).

2-Amino-5-aryl-1,3,4-thiadiazoles(I) were prepared as described earlier⁷.

N-(5-aryl-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl)aceta/benzamidines(II): These were prepared according to the method of Misra and Husain⁸. These were recrystallised from aqueous ethanol, and are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1—N-(5-ARYL-1,3,4-THIADIAZOL-2-YL) ACETA/BENZAMIDINES(II)

Sl. No.	R	Yield %	m.p. °C	Molecular formula	N (%) Found	N (%) Calcd.
R' = Phenyl						
1.	<i>o</i> -Chloro	66	170	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{11}\text{ClN}_4\text{S}$	17.65	17.80
2.	<i>p</i> -Chloro	70	240	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{11}\text{ClN}_4\text{S}$	17.67	17.80
3.	<i>p</i> -Fluoro	68	163	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{11}\text{FN}_4\text{S}$	18.68	18.79
4.	<i>p</i> -Hydroxy	72	175	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_4\text{OS}$	18.74	18.91
5.	<i>o</i> -Nitro	54	148-52 ^d	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_5\text{O}_2\text{S}$	21.28	21.53
6.	<i>m</i> -Nitro	60	115-18 ^d	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_5\text{O}_2\text{S}$	21.44	21.53
7.	<i>p</i> -Nitro	62	128-30	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_5\text{O}_2\text{S}$	21.37	21.53
R' = Methyl						
8.	H	55	178	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_4\text{S}$	25.88	25.66
9.	<i>o</i> -Chloro	64	178-80	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_9\text{ClN}_4\text{S}$	22.21	22.17
10.	<i>p</i> -Chloro	72	254	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_9\text{ClN}_4\text{S}$	22.10	22.17
11.	<i>p</i> -Fluoro	52	130	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_9\text{FN}_4\text{S}$	23.69	23.72
12.	<i>p</i> -Hydroxy	45	215	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_9\text{N}_4\text{OS}$	23.95	23.93
13.	<i>o</i> -Nitro	70	190-92	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{N}_5\text{O}_2\text{S}$	26.64	26.61
14.	<i>m</i> -Nitro	60	185-89 ^d	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{N}_5\text{O}_2\text{S}$	26.54	26.61
15.	<i>p</i> -Nitro	50	188-91 ^d	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{N}_5\text{O}_2\text{S}$	26.27	26.61

d = with decomposition.

Fungicidal Screening

The fungicidal activity was evaluated by agar-plate⁹ technique against *A. niger* and *A. flavus* at the concentrations 100 ppm and 10 ppm. The number of replications in each case was three. The percentage inhibitions by various compounds are recorded in Table 2.

TABLE 2—FUNGICIDAL SCREENING

Compound Serial as in Table 1	Average Percentage Inhibition — <i>A. niger</i> Concentrations used		Inhibition after 96 hours Organism — <i>A. flavus</i> Concentrations used	
	100 ppm	10 ppm	100 ppm	10 ppm
1	34.0	18.3	30.2	11.7
2	40.0	25.2	45.3	23.5
3	35.4	18.1	38.0	08.6
4	42.5	19.0	32.7	12.3
5	36.7	20.8	39.5	21.2
6	31.6	19.9	34.1	17.9
7	27.0	19.2	23.6	12.7
8	20.3	08.8	18.4	08.1
9	32.4	15.6	29.2	09.3
10	39.1	21.7	32.6	16.4
11	34.5	16.8	28.9	12.6
12	39.6	18.5	38.2	15.0
13	33.3	18.3	31.7	12.1
14	32.8	15.1	28.6	09.5
15	20.3	13.5	20.1	08.9

$$\% \text{ Inhibition} = \frac{(C - T) \times 100}{C}$$

where, C = Diameter of fungus colony in control plates after 96 hours.

T = Diameter of fungus colony in treated plates after 96 hours.

Results and Discussion

It is evident from the fungicidal data (Table 2) that the amidines(II) were toxic to both the fungal species in varied degrees. However, the magnitude of their fungitoxicities was not so incentive as might be expected from: (i) the combination of the thiadiazole and amidine moieties, and (ii) the possible ability of the amidines to chelate essential metals (Fig. 1), required in the metabolism of fungi, which has been suggested as the probable mechanism of action of many fungicides and bactericides¹⁰⁻¹⁴.

Fig. 1

The amidines(II) where $R' = C_6H_5$ (compound Nos. 1-7) were more potent than the corresponding amidines(II) where $R' = CH_3$ (compound Nos. 8-15), but the difference in their activities is marginal. Likewise, the compound Nos. 8-15 were more toxic to *A. niger* than to *A. flavus*.

There was significant alteration in the fungicidal activity with the change in the relative positions of the substituents. For example, the amidines having *p*-chlorophenyl group were considerably more toxic than the corresponding amidine possessing *o*-chlorophenyl group (compound Nos. 1, 2 and 9, 10). Similarly, in case of the amidines with nitrophenyl group, variation in the fungitoxicity with the change in the relative positions of the nitro group was in the order: $o > m > p$ (compound Nos. 5, 6, 7 and 13, 14, 15).

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